

Narratives of Reconstruction: Metamodern Agency in Selected

Terry Pratchett's Children's Fiction

This paper examines selected children's fiction by Terry Pratchett using the theory of metamodernism, a current structure of feeling that oscillates between a typically modern commitment and a markedly postmodern detachment¹. It explores the portrayal of the child characters and the experience of childhood when faced with conflicts brought on by the current modernity which is shaped by geopolitical, financial and ecological conflicts². In *Only You Can Save Mankind* (1992), *The Amazing Maurice and His Educated Rodents* (2001) and *Nation* (2008), the child and childlike characters realise that many metanarratives such as conventional social systems and political constructs that make up their society have resulted in dire consequences. To solve conflicts, the characters take the existing systems, deconstruct and then reconstruct it into new solutions. To achieve reconstruction, they first oscillate between the existing ways and their doubt towards it, as well as between childhood and responsibilities that children do not normally undertake. They also oscillate between states of powerfulness and powerlessness but manage nonetheless to construct their own sense of agency. At the end of stories, the characters all look forward to the future with a hopeful eye, but one that is aware of possible dire ramifications and thus in the metamodern spirit, become prepared to continuously deconstruct and reconstruct the world as they go. This paper attempts to formulate a new way to portray and analyse childhood in the metamodern epoch, as portrayed in the selected books.

¹ Timotheus Vermeulen and Robin van den Akker. "Notes on Metamodernism." *Journal of Aesthetics and Culture*. (2) 2010. Web.

² Ibid.